

is that there is no financial institution behind bitcoin. That is, there is no central bank that prints it. The blockchain knows the amount of bitcoins in circulation. The number of bitcoins is limited. This prevents inflation, it can only deflate, meaning that money can only gain value over time. [6]

Apparently, since the first money was issued in these lands, the evolution of endless forms of payment has been accelerating. Business models updated by the digital economy require rewriting all the rules of the game related to the payment process. Moreover, these developments, together with other innovations expected in the future, will subject all parties to a stronger change. It is possible to predict that these innovations will have faster and more serious effects, especially with Open Banking, Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) and decentralized stable digital currencies. However, it is useful to recognize that our time as a country is running out as countries around the world move forward at a breathtaking pace, especially in digital currencies.[7]

References

1. Mammadov Z.F., (2012): "International currency-credit relations and the monetary-credit system of foreign countries", Baku, "Nasir" publishing house, 423 pages.
2. Saleh Mammadov, "Digital transition and the need to accelerate scientific and technological development" Baku (2021), 379 pages
3. Saleh Mammadov, "Digital manat (CBDC) and cashless money circulation". ADAU, lecture text, 2021 Ganja
4. Ecem Turgut, Okyay Ucan "Econometric time series analysis of cryptocurrency and blockchain technology". Istanbul: Hyperayin, 2021 pages. 229
5. Michael J. Sasey Paul Vigne Age of Cryptocurrency: "Bitcoin and Digital Currency Challenge the Global Economic System". Ice summers - 2020 page 480
6. Khanboubi and Boulmakoul, "Digital Transformation Metamodel in Banking" – article. Researchgate 2019, p.1-7
7. Shaw, L. (2016) "The Meanings of New Money: Social Constructions of Value in the Rise of Digital Currencies", Doctoral dissertation, University of Washington, vol 16, No. 4, p. 45
8. <https://www.coinbase.com/tr/learn/crypto-basics/what-is-cryptocurrency>

PRINCIPLES OF BUSINESS ETHICS AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

In connection with the development of business relations in modern times, taking an objective approach to the events occurring in the work environment and observing the principles of human rights protection is considered one of the most important factors in the direction of business development. So, business subjects should have a pragmatic, modern economic thinking in their activities, but also develop the ethics of business relations and protect the ethical values of business management. It would be a naive approach to imagine effective business management in a globalized world without personnel with high ethical standards. Currently, there are many problems in the field of business management in Azerbaijan. One of them is that the application of elements of business ethics and corporate social responsibility in the work environment are not at a desired level. It is for this reason that in recent years, expanding reforms in the direction of increasing corporate social responsibility and further strengthening the fight against corruption for the development of business and the formation of a healthy competitive environment in Azerbaijan has been considered as one of the priority issues. The main goal here is to improve the competitive environment in business, to create conditions for the application of business ethics and social responsibility principles in the work process based on a working mechanism. All these mentioned issues characterize how important it is to follow the principles of ethical behavior and corporate social responsibility in the business environment in terms of business development.

Keywords: business ethics, social responsibility, competition, human resources, education, management.

Business relations are an integral part of modern society today. Business relations are currently developing in the economic and political spheres of society, and at the same time are regulated according to legal norms. All these mentioned are carried out in accordance with the Corporate governance code. In order to ensure long-term success in the market, expectations of honesty,

fairness, respect for competitors, and expectations of high ethical standards are important conditions. It is also considered as the concept of "Business ethics".

Some experts consider the phrase "business ethics" to be one of the most famous oxymoron phrases in the world. It should be noted that oxymorons are expressions formed by opposite words. That is, although

ethics is a word related to morals and upbringing, business is understood more as a chaotic, self-interested activity.

However, today the phrase "Business ethics" is quite popular. In particular, the ethical aspects of business are studied and promoted in the developed countries of the world.

Business ethics is the consideration of others (employees, shareholders, customers, investors, government, society, etc.) in business activities and business decisions.

Public relations and Strategic Planning are based on two concepts. The first is a step-by-step planning system for learning how to develop an effective communications program. Second, effective creativity relies on careful and deep planning rather than inspiration. The map doesn't show you where to go; instead, it helps you explore possibilities. You consider options, choose one of them, identify alternatives and prepare for unexpected situations. In short, you plan. Then you get behind the rudder, hit the road, and start putting this plan into action.

The subject of ethics is not all human activities, but primarily moral actions that emphasize morality. In Greek, the Latin equivalent of the term "ethos" comes from the word "mos", which means both custom and character. The word morality is also derived from the word mos. It has the same meaning as custom. Thus, morality and ethics form the subject of ethics. In the context of professional ethics, morality refers to the rules of conduct that must be followed in a certain profession, a profession that is directly related to a person. These general value judgments are used to assess the value of what people do in their relationships with other people.

There are certain rules of ethics. Ethical understanding and the formation of conscious social institutions require a healthy sharing and communication in this institution. Otherwise, the society is considered unhealthy. Man decides to behave ethically or not with his individual consciousness. The individual must make moral decisions alone. A person who acts in accordance with ethical behavior makes it a habit to achieve the desired good by understanding the consequences of his behavior. This person is also a person who can establish an ethical relationship with the other party.

On the other hand, the rule-governed people are willing to do whatever they are told due to the leadership's ignorance and lack of control. Loyalty causes the people to show excessive interest and respect for their leaders. Because government officials have such kind of expectations. Domestic politics is a big obstacle for citizens who lack political support, do not know people at the management level, and have poor purchasing power.

According to Pieper, ethics is based on connections between theory, knowledge, and evidence from practice. Its principle includes freedom and responsibility to be moral. According to Kant, the freedom of the will is the incomparable principle of all moral laws and corresponding duties. For this reason, there is individuality in the manager's actions and decisions to fulfill

his responsibilities to the environment and his superiors. The ethical nature of individual decisions is complicated by some law violations and arbitrariness of the bureaucratic structure. If the decisions and actions of an official are not compatible with the interests of the people, it creates distrust in the governed. Deliberately creating difficulties for people, delaying work, hiding complete information, etc. is not considered ethical behavior.

According to Wolfgang Looss, a manager must convince people as a driving force to realize his vision. Persuasion is an important element here. The main goal in the development of vision is to create a harmony between expressions and behavior. We try to practice what we say. This ensures harmony. A leader who will form the necessary vision for the implementation of ethical values within the company must establish an ethical relationship with employees, customers and other people with whom he communicates. For this, the leader must be sensitive to ethical values.

Violations of ethical principles have been found in many famous companies in the world. The most famous of such cases is the event that resulted in the bankruptcy of the Enron (USA) company in 2001. Thus, Enron's management deceived the public for the sake of short-term interests by hiding the company's expenses and creditors. Similar cases happened in companies like Xerox and Worldcom.

Competitive conditions also play a big role for business to function normally. Competitive conditions are ensured when neither buyers nor sellers dominate the market. Perfect competition is also a key driver of growth. Note that in normal competitive markets, companies do not directly participate in price formation. The market price is formed as a result of demand (interests of buyers) and supply (interests of sellers). In this case, any company that can pay its expenses at the market price can stay in the market.

One of the distinguishing aspects of the evolution of entrepreneurship has been the promotion of attributes such as ethics and social responsibility. Moreover, at the current historical stage, these attributes have become the factors on which the commercial success of the entrepreneur largely depends. These characteristics are usually called business attributes. However, considering that there are no significant differences between business and entrepreneurship, we associate these characteristics with both terms.

The impact of social responsibility on the company's decisions is not small. For example, if the financial situation of the company necessitates a reduction in the number of employees, the management may give up, even temporarily, realizing that this decision will create an unemployment problem. On the other hand, from an ethical point of view, they think that the company has been doing well until now thanks to these employees. In this sense, companies understand their moral responsibility towards employees.

Many advanced companies that understand the role of social responsibility have even created a social responsibility department. In addition, some companies conduct social audits to check the current state of social responsibility.

One of the characteristics of modern business is that as productivity increases, fewer human resources

are required to produce goods and services. As a result, a number of workers lose their jobs.

Figure 1. Pyramid of corporate responsibility level

First, the term "Corporate Social Responsibility" (Corporate Social Responsibility) appeared directly, moral corporate social responsibility principles based on internal and external sources are also expressed as business principles. Both the social contract theory and the theory of influence of all interested agents of the environment are reflected in foreign sources authored by leading scientists of the modern era. The concept of internal resources is based on the meaning of the organization as a "moral agent". The existence of a business solely for the sole purpose of making a profit is questionable. An institute of business ethics and voluntary business obligations is being formed, which carries out its activities by making contributions to improve the quality of life of the society as a whole. As a result, the term "Corporate Social Responsiveness" (Corporate Social Responsiveness), which is understood as the company's ability to understand social impact and embody it in management processes and decisions, appears [2.p. 41]. A little later, "Corporate Social Performance" (Corporate Social Performance) term is being formed. Currently, the social responsibility of business

is included in the strategic goal of the company. Without this direction, it is impossible to imagine a successful company that aspires to play the role of a leader in the market. Thus, we can say that the concept of CSR is increasingly included in the category of strategic management of the company. is integrated.

Corporate social responsibility is a very broad concept. However, this concept combines several key elements. These are the following:

- regulation of crisis situations;
- safety of production process;
- safety of the produced product;
- environmental ethics;
- the impact of business on the life of the local population;
- ethical attitude to the culture and history of the people;
- ft- education and business.

Today, two fundamental periods can be distinguished in the formation of corporate social responsibility. The first period is based on the "principles-processes-results" chain, which reflects the logic of concept formation.

Figure 2. CSR model based on the "principles-processes-results" chain

As you can see, corporate social responsibility is a very broad concept. However, this concept combines several key elements. These are the following:

Regulation of crisis situations. The upheavals in Western industry in the 1970s and 1980s: high inflation resulting from increased prices and costs of energy carriers, additional costs related to compliance with legislation aimed at reducing environmental pollution and social protection of society, and a number of other costs from business people demanded a revision of the principles of corporate social responsibility. Milton Friedman, the harbinger of these tendencies, wrote: businessmen should be allowed to return to their main business, making money, and the government should take care of the needs of society using the money received from business in the form of taxes[]. In order to maximize profits, businessmen cut costs on worker safety equipment, new equipment, and staff training, which inevitably leads to tragedy. This incident led to the fact that many companies created their own crisis recovery programs, which became an integral part of the work of managers, and security techniques were re-examined in business. In order to regulate the crisis situation, it is necessary to have a plan to get rid of the crisis situation, the crisis should be identified quickly and urgent measures should be taken.

2. Safety of production process. Of course, it is impossible to take into account all the unfortunate events in advance, but each company can assess the probability factor of the problems that may occur, take the usual precautions, and accurately distribute the tasks among the employees to eliminate the crisis. It must be admitted that in our mentality there is no special respect for safety rules. A welder with glasses on his forehead, a surgeon operating without gloves, a driver smoking a cigarette at a gas station are quite typical scenes. How many offices and restaurants with a high probability of fire have fire extinguishers? Or how many drivers have bandages, iodine and sutures in their medicine boxes?

There are many simple ways to follow safety techniques to protect individuals or companies from accidents.

3. Safety of the manufactured product. Business companies must be responsible for the safety of the manufactured product, the quality of the product released is suitable for its advertisement.

4. Environmental ethics. In the 1970s, a series of disasters in the West, particularly in the oil industry, resulted in the transformation of environmental protection from a local movement into an everyday issue of national politics. This resulted in the creation of a \$1 billion Oil Spill Relief Fund in the oil sector and the passage of the Oil Spill Environmental Pollution Act in 1991 by the US Congress.

5. The impact of business on the lives of the local population The provisions of the Code of Ethics forbid disturbing the peace of the local population or causing certain disturbances to the local population where the business is located. Unfortunately, we have accepted printing houses and restaurants on the first floor of residential buildings, which makes life unbearable for residents.

6. Ethical attitude to the culture and history of the people.

7. Education and business. Most companies sponsor training programs or hire interns to teach job skills. This practice is widespread mainly in the summer, that is, during vacations and student vacations. Such experience is mutually beneficial, as interns acquire necessary job skills and companies gain employees who work for free. Some companies use training elements successfully. There are a number of specific problems in Western corporate ethics that are not of interest to our companies at the current stage of building a market economy. This is primarily the excessive use of resources by a small group of developed countries on the one hand, and hunger in developing countries on the

other. In Western countries, such a debate cannot subside, to what extent should the Western society help the third world? []. Corporate social responsibility involves regular accountability of business to the public. For example, covering the activity of a company that affects the environment or has high social importance in the mass media, or publishing it in the form of a booklet[63]. Public disclosure of the company's annual profit and loss report (which may include a social report) is also very important. Transparency means that businesses must publicly discuss important planned projects.

Ethical obligations that apply to professional business also belong to the self-employed. Their unity in professional associations should be considered the main factor of the society in which they are now. In other cases, there will be no effective mechanisms for ethical compliance by freelancers. At this time, it can be objected that there are methods of influencing freelancers in market relations. However, it is not even considered correct to assume a high professional level of services offered by them. In many situations, differentiating a product or service that meets personal needs in the market, such as groceries or laundry service, creates many difficulties for the customer. When choosing goods made on the basis of high technology, that is, when choosing household appliances produced by companies, the customer should pay attention to the advertising brochures of the manufacturing enterprise or its sphere of influence.

At present, many entrepreneurs in our republic, when establishing any close business relations with businessmen and businessmen from foreign countries, sometimes they encounter many difficult and equally complicated moments in the process of making and making decisions because they do not know exactly the principles of the western management system. Because foreign investors, when establishing relations with local companies and organizations, first of all pay attention to factors such as trust in the company, its compliance with international standards and local rules and laws, as well as gaining reputation among the population. From this point of view, the concept of business ethics is more relevant. In many developed countries of the world, they approach this issue more carefully and more responsibly. Because, without taking into account the competence of the company in the field of business ethics, it is impossible to establish commercial and economic relations between the states in a normal form. The concept of "Business Ethics" in business management brings regularity to the relations of employees

with each other and with managers, directly helps to increase productivity and the quality of the work done. When we say business ethics, we understand the ethical norms and rules of conduct designed and developed for the activity of a company. However, this issue has other important aspects. This "Business Ethics" consists of laws and indicators that show that this organization is a big family and that every employee working within the enterprise is a part of this organization (family). Therefore, by using only these rules and laws of business ethics, it is possible to increase the company's competitiveness and labor productivity to the maximum extent, increase and improve the quality of the work done by employees.

Adhering to the norms of human value and ethical behavior in business activity will contribute to the solution of many problems encountered in business life. Thus, the business ethics weakness that we often complain about with the implementation of the principles of business ethics and social responsibility in the business environment; it will be possible to minimize many negative situations such as bribery, corruption, rigging of tenders, production of low-quality and counterfeit goods, tax evasion, luxury consumption, excessive profit seeking, imaginary exports.

References

1. Aliyev M.A., Hamidov H.I., Huseynli A.T. Corporate governance. Textbook. Baku: "Economics University" Publishing House, 2011. - p.484
2. "Business ethics". Resources for Azerbaijani businessmen. / R. Safaraliyeva, S. Mammadov, V. Gaziyeu. Baku. 2004. – p.171
3. Simatov A.A. Problems of implementation of anti-corruption policy in the activity of executive bodies of state power // Vlast. 2014. No. 11. C. p.97-100
4. PRIMAUX Patrick, STIEBER John; "Profit Maximization: The Ethical Mandate of Business", Journal of Business Ethics, Vol. 13 No. 4, 1994, p. 287-294.
5. ERSÖZ, Halis Yunus "Corporate Social Responsibility", Business Ethics with Theoretical and Applied Dimensions, (Compiled by: Sabri Orman, Zeki Parlak), Istanbul, ITO Publishing, 2009
6. ÖZDEMİR, Süleyman "Overview of Academic Work Ethics Studies in Today's Turkey", Work Ethics with Theoretical and Applied Dimensions, (Editor: Sabri Orman), Istanbul, ITO Publishing, 2009, p. 301–336.